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IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON THE IGALA TRADITIONAL BELIEF SYSTEM

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Abstract: Globalization, characterized by increasing interconnectedness and interdependence of economies, cultures and societies has profoundly influenced traditional beliefs system worldwide. This paper examines the impact of globalization on the Igala traditional belief system, a cultural heritage of the people. Deeply rooted in indigenous practices, rituals and cosmologies, the Igala belief system emphasizes ancestral worship, spiritual symbiosis and community cohesion. Globalization through the spread of western values, technological advancements and cross-cultural exchanges has introduced new religions and secular ideologies that challenge and interact with these traditional beliefs. This process has led to both the preservation and transformation of Igala traditions as the people especially younger generations embrace modern lifestyle while still engaging with cultural heritage hence, a shift in religious practices, modifications in communal rituals and a redefined role for traditional authorities. This paper therefore concludes by highlighting the dynamics of how globalization has both eroded and reinforced aspects of Igala traditional belief system, and suggest pathways for balancing modern influences with preservation of the cultural identity of the Igala people of kogi state. To achieve this, the paper adopts the use of primary and secondary sources of data collection which involve in-depth oral interview and extensive review of related literature.

Introduction

The Igala traditional belief system has been greatly affected by the phenomenon of

globalization. The increased interconnectedness and interdependence among countries of the world has brought about significant changes in

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the traditional belief system worldwide. The traditional beliefs and practices that were once strongly ingrained in Igala society are now facing challenges of extinction. One of the main impacts of globalization on the Igala traditional belief system is the introduction of new ideas and values. With the exposure to different cultures and ideologies, the traditional beliefs of the people are being challenged and replaced by foreign ideas. This has led to decline in the practice of certain rituals and custom, and a shift towards a more modern and westernized beliefs. As globalization spreads, traditional practices and beliefs are often seen as outdated and fetishes. This has also led to loss of cultural identity and decrease in the pride and preservation of the people's culture and traditions. As a result, the people especially, the younger generation are becoming more detached from their cultural heritage and are fast embracing a more "globalized and westernized beliefs".

Furthermore, globalization has also had economic impact on the Igala traditional belief system. For instance, the commercialization and commoditization of traditional rituals and beliefs have changed the dynamics of the belief system. Many traditional practices like *Ifa* divination and *Egbunu* rituals are now being performed for monetary gains rather than for cultural and spiritual purposes.¹ This has equally led to the

loss of authenticity and integrity in the traditional beliefs and practices in Igalaland.

From the foregoing therefore, the impact of globalization on the Igala traditional belief system is undeniable. The changes brought about by globalization have reshaped the cultural landscape and challenged the traditional beliefs and practices among the Igala people.

Historical Background of the Igala people

Opinion differs among scholars on the authentic origin of the Igala people; the argument revolved around the migration of the people to their present place of abode. For example, the late Attah of Igala, Alhaji Ali Obaje in Saidu Ajodo told "Nigerian magazine" editors that... the first wave of migration into this country (Igalaland) seems to have taken place about 12th century A.D and was led by Amina, a zaria princess and warrior, who fought her way to Idah. She came with Hausa and Nupe followers whose descendants are associated with the Jema'a and Ibo quarters in the town.² In 1969 while fielding question from Mr. Michael Asaju, the same Attah held the view that, the Igala people came from the Arab country of Yemen and were in the present Nigeria at the same time as the founding fathers of Yoruba, the Jukuns and the Beriberis (Kanuris of Boronu).³ Contributing to the debate, scholars such as Captain F. Bying Hall suggests that the Igalas, Idomas and Igbiras are descendants of the Jukuns. Yet others hold the view that the Igala are a branch of Yorubas on the

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account of language and cultural affinity.⁴ Yusufu Etu in Saidu was quoted as saying that, “no one can say with certainty the particular place Igala people came from.” He further argued that, there is no reason against suggesting that Igala people speaking a kwa language were the people who occupied their present location from time immemorial.⁵ This suggests that, there was never a time that the Igalaland was vacant or occupied by any other group(s) other than the Igala. However, C.A. Temple in Achoba et’al has argued that the Igala people descended from the *Apa* who lived in the neighbourhood of *Ibi* for many years but have to flee from the *Jukun* in canoe down the Benue in about 1490 A.D under their chief, Idoko.⁶

From the foregoing, it is therefore not very clear about the real source of the Igala but what is clear is that the Igala people constitute one of the major ethnic groups in modern Nigeria with distinct language and culture. They effectively occupy the major part of the land on the eastern flank of river Niger. Pockets of the Igala could also be found in Enugu, Delta and Anambara States of Nigeria.

Originally, the Igalaland lies within the lower Niger basin and is bounded by the Niger River in the west and the river Benue in the north. Therefore, Igalaland begins at Adamugu, a few kilometres north of Onitsha, and continues up to the confluence from where it protrudes linearly

north-eastwards along the Benue, terminating at Amagede in the Igala-Agatu boundary area.⁷

The land described above is presently located in the eastern senatorial district of kogi state where the Igala are the dominant ethnic group.

The traditional beliefs and practices among the Igala people are deeply rooted in their history and cultural heritage, which means that, the Igala ethnic group has an identifiable cultural heritage, ritual practices and beliefs which are unique to them.

Central to these Igala traditional beliefs is the worship of a pantheon of deities and ancestral spirits. The Igala cosmology is characterized by a reverence for the supreme deity known as *Ojocamachala*, the creator and the highest God who governs the universe and oversees the affairs of mankind. This belief in the supreme deity is complemented by the veneration of various other lesser deities and spirits, each responsible for specific aspects of their lives and nature. These deities according to Henry Emusa includes; water spirit (*Alijenu*), spirit Husband/wife (*Ikpakachi*), earth goddess (*Ebo-Ane*), fairies or Bush Babies (*Ichekpa*), Twin (*Iye-Unyi’Ejima*), symbols of good luck (*Egbunu*) and the ancestral spirits.⁸

The Egbunu Deity

One significant deity in the Igala traditional religion or beliefs is the *Egbunu* deity. According to Okpanachi, *Egbunu* is an in-born deity especially, for people who were born with their

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umbilical cord tied around their neck at birth.⁹ It is a personal deity that an individual is born with. Among the Igala people, any child born with his/her umbilical cord tied around his/her neck automatically has this personal deity which he/she must always make sacrifices and prayers to for open doors. In the words of Joseph Abimaje, the Egbunu deity has the capacity to bless and withhold the blessings of its “supposed servants”.¹⁰ What this means is that, Egbunu deity is a personalized deity and that, no two individuals have the same Egbunu deity unlike the supreme deity that is for everybody. There is usually a special white plate called *Ugba'Egbunu* hung at the back of the house of the parents, usually the father's house of the “servants” which serve as the point of contact with the deity. Inside this white plate are items of sacrifice like, beans, rice, maize white chalk, red feather, a piece of white cloth and sometimes calico and red oil.¹¹ Apart from having a special white plate (*Ugba'Egbunu*, as point of contact with the deity, there is another means of reaching out to this deity which is, drawing a circle on the ground at the backyard of the house or residence of the servant of the *Egbunu* deity for the purpose of sacrifices.¹² This circle represents the white plate in the event that the individual concerned decides not to have a designated plate for it. According to Ele, a sacrifice for the *Egbunu* deity unlike sacrifices or rituals for some deities is not seasonal but can be performed anytime as the

situation demand, in fact the ritual can be performed two to three times or more in a year.¹³ It should be noted that, this deity also exists among the Bassa Nge people. However, there is a sharp difference in how this deity is venerated between the Igala people and the Bassa Nge people. For the Igala, it is a personal or a personalised deity while, among the Bassa Nge people it is more of a centralised deity. Also, among the Bassa Nge people, it is represented in a masquerade called *Ndakogboya*, which handles cases of infidelity, witchcraft, misfortune, settlement of disputes, criminal justice administration, and punishment of erring members of the society as well as entertainment. Conversely, among the Igala, it is not represented in masquerade form.¹⁴ However, the similarity in the name should not be taken to mean that one borrowed the deity from the other.

Ikpakachi Deity

Another deity in the pantheon of deities in Igala traditional belief system is the *Ikpakachi* deity. It is a water deity that is responsible for the general wellbeing of the individual, especially as regards marriage and health.¹⁵ Like the *Egbunu* deity, *Ikpakachi* equally possess powers to bless as well as block people's chances in life. While making the distinction between *Ikpakachi* and *Egbunu* deities, Okpanachi narrated that, while, *Egbunu* is an in-born deity, while *Ikpakachi* is a post birth deity.¹⁶ According to him, at birth, a child comes in contact with the *Ikpakachi* deity

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through water. That is, When a child is born in traditional Igala setting or society, the mid-wives usually deep their fingers in water and put a drop of such water in the child's mouth as his/her first water intake.¹⁷ This water, traditions has it that, if it is a rain water, the supreme deity (*Ojochamachala*) becomes the child's *Ikpakachi* and if it is stream/river water then, the water goddess becomes his/her *Ikpakachi*.¹⁸ This deity also requires periodic sacrifices from its "servant", failure to do so attract punishment from the deity. The *umo* or *omi-umo* is usually the point of contact with the *Ikpakachi* deity especially for the purpose of sacrifices. This *omi-umo* is the water collected in a bottle from the stream or river where the first water given to the child was fetched from buried half-way at the feet of any three where the parents decide to bury it in their backyard. It is at the feet of this bottle that sacrifices to appease and make supplication to the *Ikpakachi* deity are performed.

The *ogonodu* rite of passage is also associated with *Ikpakachi* deity. The performance of the *ogonodu* rite of passage (*et'ogonodu*) is a process whereby a teenager both male and female is initiated into adulthood especially before they start having intercourse with the opposite sex. In an oral interview with Ele Amodu, any teenager especially male teenager who skip the *ogonodu* ritual and start having sexual intercourse with the opposite sex would usually have malfunctioned manhood in future.¹⁹ Such

situation can only be remedied when such a person present himself for the *ogonodu* rite of passage ritual. Apart from malfunction of manhood for the male children as punishment for skipping the *ogonodu* ritual, both the male and female children usually experience a situation where they will have sexual intercourse in their dreams and they wake up the will be wet. When this happens it is usually attributed to the *Ikpakachi* deity. This situation is sometimes responsible for delay in marriage for both genders. When a young man or woman is experiencing delay in getting married, it is believed among the Igala people that he or she has spiritual husband or wife. Anytime you hear about spiritual husband of wife especially among the Igala people, they referring to this deity (*Ikpakachi*).

Belief in Ancestors/Living Dead

The Igala people believe that the dead never actually die, rather, they remain in immortal state. They are buried within their homes and so their spirit may be close to their families. Igala people venerate ancestors based on their belief that the dead continue to exist after their physical death. The aim in Igala culture is to enjoy the attraction of favours and care on the living from the ancestors. Ancestor's veneration is not the same with the worship of a deity or deities. While the ancestors were once human persons, the deities are created spirits that minister with some capacity under the Supreme

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Being. Ancestors are better closed for human needs because they were once humans.

Mbiti has also collaborated that ancestors understand the language of Man and Spirits, that they are at the centre between human and the gods, as well as the Supreme God. He expresses: The living dead are bilingual: they speak the language of men with whom they lived until recently, and they speak the language of spirits and of God to whom they are drawing nearer ontologically....it is through the living dead that the spirit world become personal to men. They are still part of their human families' and people have personal memories of them.... They return to their human families from time to time and share meals with them, however symbolically, they know and have interest in what is going on in the family. When they appear, which is generally to the oldest members of the household, they are recognised by name; they enquire about family affairs and many even of impending danger or rebuke those who failed to follow their special instructions. They are the guardians of family affairs, traditions, ethnics and activities.²⁰

Ancestors are being welcomed in a hospitable manner through the offering of libation. If people neglect to give food and libation or fail to observe instructions that they gave before dying, then misfortunes and sufferings would be interpreted as resulting from the anger of the living dead.²¹ It is now imperative to state that majority of Igala

people now neglect their traditional practice of the ancestor veneration. This is because, in recent years, the sweeping value of Western globalization conveyed through Western language, English and discriminate through global information communication technology, the internet, as well as the counter penetration of Western religion has completely eroded, destabilized and destroyed this virtuous culture of Igala people.

Igala Family Moral Values

The family is one of the institutions that were mostly affected by the problem of globalization. The traditional Igala family system where every child is a child of all and all join hands together to train a child, is giving way to an individualistic exclusive nuclear family system. This is where the influence of the community and even the extended family system gives ways to that of the parents of the child alone. Folklores used by the traditional Igala family of African nation to instil morals in the minds of children have almost died and are replaced by satellite television and video games. The folklores which has rich moral lessons has almost been abandoned for the home video and cyber-networking and other internet based social networks like Facebook, 2go, WhatsApp to mention just a few which now connect children and youths to people from diverse cultures which in turn impact negatively on them. Parents now have little or no control over their children's social activities and who

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they interact with. With the use of internet enabled handsets, children now have access to a wide variety of websites which expose them to obscene materials that their parents find difficult to censor. This situation keeps on widening the gap in the extended family system and many a time alienates the children from their parents.²²

Erosion of Sense of Communal Living

In the Igala traditional setting, Igala people live together as one. One does not need to be related by blood before one sees one's neighbours as family members. Then, people have a sense of communal living. They are free with one another, as they share food, clothing materials and personal effects together. It is a society where one could correct or scold another person's child/children for wrong doing without the parent of the recipient raising an eyebrow.²³ Discipline and enforcement of moral values then was a collective responsibility. The following circumstances were vividly captured by Mbiti when he expressed that 'I am because we are. And since we are therefore, I am.'²⁴ The situation is different now.

Individualism has replaced Igala people sense of collective coexistence. Everyone does his/her own thing in each one's desired way. Everything boils down to 'me', 'self', 'mine' and 'myself': Individualistic tendencies now permeate the society, because so is the norm in the Western society. Sense of family relationship and brotherhood are gradually waning down. Since

there is no longer trust, everyone is suspicious of his/her neighbours, friends, family members, co-workers, among others. One dare not scold, admonish or discipline another person's child/children without the consent of the parents. The ward/wards in question could insult anyone who dares, let alone the parents. Everyone now look out to protect individual interest. Hence, the common slang among youth nowadays: "You are on your own (OYO)."²⁵

Belief in Respect for Custodians of Culture and Traditions

The Igala people have a lot of respect for elders, aged, community leaders, authorities and public office holders. They see these categories of people as those who are custodians of culture and tradition, and those who are vested with the power to lead and guide them. They have high regard for them. In short, they show respect to whoever it is due. Therefore, younger one do not only go on errands for their parents, but for people who might not be related to them by blood, but are older than them. People accord themselves respect even in greeting. Aged age mates bow to their peers while greeting, the female younger one genuflect and the males bow among the Igala socio-cultural setting in North-Central Nigeria.

Also, common among the Igala people is the tendency of the younger ones to ease someone older of the latter's luggage, when the former comes in contact with them. The reverse is the

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case today. Most youth watch adult carrying luggage and would just walk pass the elderly one(s). Majority of the youths find it difficult to greet nowadays. Igala society is now following what is norm in the Western world, where according respect to parents, elders and authorities might not be compulsory. This explains the way they hurl insults on parents, authorities and institutions. Hence, the various hate speeches in the electronic and social media, which cumulates in the reason why the society is losing decorum gradually.²⁶

Traditional Diagnostic and Therapeutic System of Care in Igalaland

Virtually every village in Igala has a medicine man or woman.²⁷ As friends of the community they are accessible to everybody and at all times. They are concerned first and foremost with diseases, sickness and misfortunes which in the Igala experience are caused by mystical forces. The Igala traditional healers have therefore to diagnose the nature of the diseases, discover its cause and apply the right treatment, together with a means of preventing its reoccurrence. It can be further explained that both physical and spiritual methods are applied to ensure good health.²⁸

The implication of the efforts made by the colonial administrators to suppress traditional medicine is enormous for the fact, that there are countless number of people now in Africa particularly among the Igala communities

striving for better health at every level of the global health care system but it remains difficult. The widen gap between the rich and the poor has denied the poor an access to better health and this adversely affect our development process. Yankuzo²⁹ asserted that the exploitation of Africa, Asian and Latin American countries by the core capitalist nations of Europe through colonial and non-colonial linkages like globalization is identified as the root cause of underdevelopment of health and medical care resources of those nations.

The Impact of Globalization on the Igala Traditional belief System

The Igala traditional belief system, characterized by its inclusive monotheistic structure, has faced significant transformations due to globalization. The global interconnectedness through technological advancements, cultural hybridization, and migration has reshaped religious practices, altered cultural values, and necessitated adaptive strategies within Igala communities. The proliferation of the internet and social media has exposed Igala communities to global religious movements, enabling access to diverse spiritual teachings and virtual communities.³⁰ While this fosters interfaith dialogue, it risks diluting traditional practices through misinformation or reduced engagement with local rituals. For instance, younger generations increasingly prioritize digital content over oral traditions like folktales, which

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historically transmitted moral values and cosmological beliefs.³¹

Global trade and migration patterns have introduced Western ideologies, such as consumerism and individualism, challenging the Igala emphasis on communal stewardship. Exposure to foreign cultures has led to syncretic practices, where elements of Christianity or Islam blend with traditional rites.³² This is called Cultural Hybridization. However, this hybridization sometimes weakens the authority of indigenous institutions, as seen in declining participation in ceremonies led by clan elders and the moral decadence where younger generation now indulge in all sorts of social vices like sexual immorality, indecent dressing as well as flagrant disregards for elders and cultural taboos.

The Igala traditional values which emphasize environmental stewardship and collective responsibility are increasingly supplanted by materialistic aspirations which are tied to global capitalism. For example, sacred forests once protected by taboos are now vulnerable to exploitation for economic gain, reflecting a prioritization of short-term benefits over long-term sustainability.³³

However, efforts to document Igala folktales and rituals using digital platforms highlight attempts to preserve cultural heritage amid globalization. Initiatives like audio recordings of oral histories and online repositories aim to bridge generational gaps, ensuring traditional knowledge survives in modern formats. In addition, some communities reinterpret rituals to address contemporary issues, such as incorporating eco-conscious messaging into ancestral veneration practices.³⁴

Conclusion

Globalization presents dual challenges and opportunities for the Igala traditional belief system. While external influences threaten to erode indigenous practices, technological tools and adaptive strategies offer pathways for preservation. Balancing openness to global exchange with intentional cultural stewardship remains critical for sustaining the Igala's unique religious identity.

¹ Interview with Ochedi Shaibu Udale, 40 years, civil servant, Lokoja, 25/8/2024

² Saidu A. "Who are the Igalas? A new perspective into Igala History, (Kadauna: Nadabo Graphics and Publishers, 2014). 13

³ Saidu A. "Who are the Igalas? A new perspective into Igala History, (Kadauna: Nadabo Graphics and Publishers, 2014). 13

⁴ Saidu A. "Who are the Igalas? A new perspective into Igala History, (Kadauna: Nadabo Graphics and Publishers, 2014). 14

⁵ Etu Y. Igala History in question and answer...

⁶ Achoba.F. et'al Nigeria Peoples and Culture (GST 103), in Audu P.A., Gbaje E.S., Abdullahi M.Y, Fashagba J.Y., and

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Auduson A.E. (ed) Directorate of General Studies, Federal University Lokoja, (Lecture notes of General studies, 2020).13

⁷ Saidu A. "Who are the Igalas"? A new perspective into Igala History, (Kaduna: Nadabo Graphics and Publishers, 2014). 10

⁸ Henry Emusa...

⁹ Interview with Okpanachi Yusuf...

¹⁰ Interview with Joseph Abimaje, 68 years, farming, Agbajo 19/8/2024

¹¹ Interview with Ochedi Shaibu Udale...

¹² Interview with Ochedi Shaibu Udale...

¹³ Interview with Ele Amodu, 56 years, herberlist, Ajekeyi, 23/8/2024

¹⁴ Interview with Nasir phd...

¹⁵ Interview with Ochedi Shaibu Udale...

¹⁶ Interview with Okpanachi Yusufu...

¹⁷ Interview with Ochedi Shaibu Dale...

¹⁸ Interview with Ochedi Shaibu Udale...

¹⁹ Interview with Ele Amodu...

²⁰ Mbiti, J. S. *African Religious and Philosophy* (London: Heinemann, 1969), 83.

²¹ Interview with Baba Faruna, Farming, 78 years, Efakwu-Eguine, 4/5/2025

²² Interview with Shedra Etuh, Civil Servant, 55 years, Ilorin, Kwara State, 2/5/2025

²³ Akinsola, Abidemi Oyinade, *Impacts of Globalisation on African Countries: The Nigerian Example*, Journal of African Social Studies (JASS) Volume 1, Number 2, 2020:50.

²⁴ Mibiti, J. S. *African Religions and Philosophy*. London: Macmill, 1969, 5.

²⁵ Akinsola, Abidemi Oyinade, *Impacts of Globalisation on African Countries: The Nigerian Example*, Journal of African Social Studies (JASS) Volume 1, Number 2, 2020:50.

²⁶ Akinsola, Abidemi Oyinade, *Impacts of Globalisation on African Countries: The Nigerian Example*, 52.

²⁷ Okpe, Nicholas Ojoajogwu. *An Assessment of the Socio-Religions Roles of Women in a Traditional Igala Society*. International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education Volume 5, Issue 8, 2018: 190.

²⁸ Okpe, Nicholas Ojoajogwu. *An Assessment of the Socio-Religions Roles of Women in a Traditional Igala Society*, 190.

²⁹ Yankuzo, Kabiru Ibrahim. *Impact of Globalization on the Traditional African Cultures*. International Letters of Social and Humanities Sciences, ISSN, Vol. 15.1:5.

³⁰ Isaiah Adujo Negedu, "The Igala Traditional Religious Belief System: Between Monotheism and Polytheism," OGIRISI: a New Journal of African Studies 10, no. 1 (2014): 124.

³¹ Negedu, "Igala Traditional Religious Belief System," 124.

³² Divinah Andrew, "The Impact of Globalization on the Traditional Religious Practices and Cultural Values: A Case Study of Kenya," International Journal of Culture and Religious Studies 4, no. 2 (2023): 8.

³³ Ojonugwa Sunday Joseph and Sunday Sule Emah, "Towards Preserving Igala Folktales," Journal of Modern European Languages and Literature 13 (2020): 74.

³⁴ Joseph and Emah, "Preserving Igala Folktales," 74.